

**GENERAL PRINCIPLES FOR ORGANIZING TRANSLATION
TRAINING**

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Qodirova Gulbakhor Turdiyevna
*Lecturer of department of foreign
languages, faculty of agro engineering
and hydro melioration, Andijan Institute
of Agriculture and Agro technologies*

Annotation: *Translation is a very complex type of speech-thinking activity, which requires the presence of specific knowledge and skills and is carried out largely intuitively. As a result of acquiring such knowledge and skills (in the process of learning or through long-term practice), an intuitive ability to properly solve translation problems develops.*

Key words: *Language interpreting, intellectual activity, professional practice, development and progress, aspects, speech-thinking activity, establishing.*

Naturally, the success of creation and the achieved level of such ability largely depend on the individual data of the student. It is possible that the most outstanding results in translation activities can only be achieved by those individuals who have an innate predisposition (talent) for this particular occupation. There are also cases when especially gifted translators, without special training and special efforts, demonstrated high translation skills from the very beginning. Of course, the success of education to a large extent depends on the organization of the educational process, curriculum and teaching methods.

So, translation should be taught as a special academic discipline, and mastering the ability to translate is not (exclusively) the prerogative of especially gifted people. This position is now generally recognized, and in all educational

institutions that train translators, students are offered classes in the theory and practice of translation. The method of teaching translation is based on the belief that a person has the ability to translate genetically, as well as the ability to master languages, although each individual has this ability to a different degree, it can be developed and brought to a professional level.

Translation training has not only a purely applied value - the creation of the necessary translation competence among students. It also performs important general linguistic and general educational functions. Translation classes encourage students to pay attention to the finest nuances of semantics and connotative aspects of language units, reveal the originality of the systemic organization and functioning of languages, the features of the “picture of the world” created by each language, the general and particular in the culture and thinking of representatives of different language communities. The creation of translation competence contributes to the comprehensive development of the personality of future translators: it forms their attentiveness and sense of responsibility, the ability to use reference books and additional sources of information, make choices, quickly make the right decisions, detect and compare numerous linguistic and extralinguistic data. The professional training of a translator presupposes a high culture, wide encyclopedic erudition, sociability, tact, constant replenishment of knowledge, and a variety of interests. All these qualities are manifested in two languages and two cultures. The content of any academic discipline is determined by the characteristics of the subject being studied and the ultimate goal of training. The essence of translation activity studies comprehends and describes the theory of translation, the provisions of which underlie the training program for future translators.

However, the main task of the translation course is not to provide students with a certain body of knowledge, but to train them to be highly qualified specialists capable of performing translations at a professional level. Therefore, a significant part of the course is devoted to the development of professional

translation skills, mastering the elements of a translation strategy and technique, and gaining experience in translating texts of varying degrees of complexity.

Translation is considered as a complex and multifaceted type of mental activity that can pursue different goals, be carried out in different conditions, in different ways and under the influence of many factors.

Like any activity, translation requires for its implementation certain knowledge, skills (conscious performance of certain actions) and skills (semi-automatic and automatic performance of certain actions), which must be created in the learning process.

Translation activities can be carried out by the translator consciously (as a result of analysis and reasonable conclusions) or intuitively. The ratio of conscious and intuitive is different for different translators and when translating different texts and under different conditions. The ability to carry out conscious and intuitive translation actions (translation competence) can be developed in the process of learning and practical work.

The implementation of translation competence occurs with the participation of the entire linguistic personality of the translator. It assumes that he has comprehensive cognitive and linguistic knowledge, broad general cultural erudition, the necessary psychological qualities and literary abilities. All these qualities should be developed and encouraged in translation training.

The task of teaching translation is not to learn any norms, rules or recipes that a translator could automatically apply in all cases, but to master the principles, methods and techniques of translation and the ability to choose and apply them differently in specific conditions, to different texts and for different purposes. Particular tasks solved by a translator in the process of translation can be typical, allowing the use of a known technique or method of solving, and individual, requiring a new solution based on the general principles of the translation strategy and taking into account the specifics of the context and situation. The search for a solution also includes conclusions about the possibility of using a known technique

or method for deciding whether it is necessary to modify it or abandon the typical one in favor of a unique, occasional one.

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